

Analysis on the Elements of Modern Packaging Design

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Conflicts of Interest

There are no conflicts to declare.

Introduction

There are more and more commodities of various categories as a result of ongoing economic development, each category of goods must be represented by packaging. China has a lengthy history, and different regions have varied production methods, lifestyles, and cultural traits. This opens a regional door for the current packaging design, and artistic treatment of these local unique materials as the basic elements of packaging can give people regional information and cultural communication, which is most easily accepted by people. A country's history and achievements are inextricably linked to its culture. China has always been known for its lengthy history, and its traditional culture is rich and stable in the evolution of civilization, which is the greatest interpretation of its rich cultural heritage. The term "regional culture" refers to the distinct regional national culture, which includes a variety of languages, cultures, and values developed by various regions and nationalities under the

ABSTRACT

Packaging is a concept of a brand, material characteristics, a full reflection of consumer psychology, has a direct impact on consumer purchases, consumer products and packaging is built to create a strong affinity instrument. China has a large landmass and a wealth of natural resources. Commodity package design has become an essential aspect of the social market economy in recent decades, especially as economic globalization has progressed. Unique packaging is the finest technique to attract customers by recognizing and reflecting the worth of goods and making them want to consume them. Packaging art design with regional cultural features has steadily become the focus of attention as regional culture has developed qualities in product packaging, which has some theoretical and practical research value. This study aims analyzes the element of design in modern packaging design; its application value is studied in combination with actual cases, and further discussed its application trend. It emphasizes on the fact that the elements of modern packaging can highlight the fun of packaging, accentuate the humanistic feelings of packaging, it is one of the driving factors for the construction of enterprise brand cultural competitiveness, and strategic importance to the development of enterprises.

Keywords: PACKAGING, DESIGN, BRAND, ELEMENT

constraints of various environments. Regional visual elements have their own historical and cultural context, reflecting the regional cultural form and representing local customs and customs.

The progressive social changes and observed mega trends occurring in the production chain induce manufacturers to take an interest in possibilities of attraction contained on product packaging, as one of the components of marketing information, is a factor significantly influencing the opinion of consumers about the product. Modern packaging illustrations are made up of many elements. At different times, the development of technology and art can always reflect the original nature of commodities. In the history of the development of China, the fusion of painting style and traditional culture is a kind of ideological sustenance for designers. They can use different painting methods to create more attractive and practical to consumers' works. Comparing traditional art paintings with modern packaging illustrations, art paintings serve a small part of the population and spread in a small area; while commercial illustrations are spread and propagated through the media, they receive a lot in a short time people's attention, coupled with its beautiful picture and image, always leading the trend, leading the fashion, eventually making the growing number of people want to buy it.

Packaging illustrations have a unique language of the times, and sometimes these languages cover the worldwide language, so that their own brands have their own characteristics and influence. Packaging is defined as a product put on the market "made of any materials, intended for storing, protection, transport, delivering or presentation of products, from raw materials to processed goods". In a similar way, packaging is defined by [S. Chudy and M. Pietraszewski \(2015\)](#). According to them, packaging is "a physical structure suitable for a product, which is designed to protect it from damage and deterioration, enable its dividing into portions and transport (utility functions) as well as to provide information on the product and present it aesthetically (promotional functions)". Packaging can also be defined as "a product which is an additional outer layer of a particular item, which should facilitate its protection against external factors, movement, storage, sale and use as well as affect the perception of the item"

According to experts, the definition of packaging should contain the following, most distinctive features of Packaging

- Protection of a product during storage and transport operations as well as during its use and, in some cases,
- protection of the environment against possible harmful effects of the product
- Simplification of production, transport and sale as well as use of products
- Necessary information about a product, above all about its consumer usefulness
- Psychological impact on a potential customer through appropriate presentation of a product.

Materials and methods

Analysis of Packaging Design Industry

Consumer products and packaging are to establish a compelling means of affinity. Packaging is the brand concept, product attributes, and a thorough reflection of consumer psychology. It has a direct impact on consumer purchases. Economic globalization has resulted in the integration of packaging and products. Packaging, as a way of achieving the value and use value of commodities, plays an incredibly essential function in the business community, particularly in the areas of manufacturing, distribution, sale, and consumption. The purpose of packaging is to protect goods, convey product information, make it simple to use and carry, enhance sales, and provide value to things. Packaging is a broad discipline that encompasses both goods and artistic duality.

Figure 1: The global packaging market, 1999-2009

Focus on Packaging Design Elements

Outstanding design works in current package art design have condensed the unique regional culture and became the audience's focus of attention. As a result, packaging art design aims to show traditional culture alongside modern society, eastern culture alongside western culture. In today's increasingly materialistic culture, good ideas are essential if we want our items to stand out amid the crowd. The key to improving the technical level of the arts and crafts business, integrating arts and crafts into modern living, and giving full play to convenience and emotional comfort is to raise the technological level of the arts and crafts industry. Diverse cultural systems emerge in different places after people have struggled with nature for a long time. The style and culture of local nationalities and folk practices, as well as the cultural remnants left by area history, were generally absorbed in the use of regional culture in modern packaging art design. The value of commodities improves significantly after packaging today, thanks to the rapid development of design discipline. Producers should think about product market positioning, sales objects, and method selection and placement. At the same time, they should gain a better understanding of the people's lifestyles and traditional taboos in the area where the products are sold before they can feel at ease. In China, there are many wonderful cultural traditions, and these fine customs

frequently have deeper connotations, all of which suggest the people's desire for a brighter future. The main source of packaging design inspiration for designers is regional culture, which not only has the distinctiveness and culture of traditional commodities, but also has the ability to influence consumers' commodity choices.

The key emphasis on positioning in a good packaging design is that the performance should be multiple, so that individuals from various locations and nationalities can have diverse objective living situations. Some words and patterns hold lovely meanings and people's aspiration for a better life throughout China's ancient history and culture. If these factors are incorporated into the product packaging design process, the end result will undoubtedly offer people a positive sensation.

The package can be treated as a set of elements that communicate messages to consumers, and the kind of message that is communicated depends on either visual or verbal elements, where verbal elements send out information and visual elements affect emotions. Visual elements is made up of color, shape (also called form), size, material and graphics while verbal elements include the name, brand, producer/country of origin, information about product, usage instructions and special offers. When the authors place 'brand' among verbal elements, this means the direct attention of the trademark and brand information rather than the entire experience of the brand, which can be built out of all elements. It is the elements of a package that influence consumers' decision making process and can determine their choices. Thus a well-designed packaging is evaluated as a competitive advantage. According to [Stewart \(2004\)](#), package design's ability to kick off an emotional dialogue with the consumer is what affects decision-making. It is the influence of emotions that make packaging very influential. [Baocheng L, Yu W. \(2006\)](#) argue that verbal components of packages do not for instance have much impact on repeated purchase that is it to say, these elements do not influence the consumer's behavior after the purchase. It is because of visual elements' impact on decision making and emotions that this essay focuses primarily on them.

The package's elements

The package can be thought of as a collection of parts that express messages to customers, and the type of message communicated is determined by visual or verbal aspects, with verbal elements conveying information and visual elements influencing emotions ([Silayoi and Speece, 2004](#)). Color, shape (also known as form), size, material, and graphics are visual aspects, whereas verbal elements include the name, brand, producer/country of origin, product information, usage directions, and special offers [Hernik J. Informacja czy manipulacja \(2013\)](#). When the writers include the word 'brand' among the verbal aspects, they are referring to the direct attention given to the trademark and brand information rather than the overall brand experience, which can be constructed from all elements.

Consumers' decision-making processes are influenced by the aspects of a package, which can decide their selections. As a result, a well-designed package is considered a competitive advantage ([Kuvykaite et. al., 2009](#)). According to [Stewart \(2004\)](#), the power of package design to initiate an emotional dialogue with the consumer influences decision-making. It is the emotional impact of packaging that makes it so powerful. According to [Hong L. \(2003\)](#) verbal components of packages, for example, do not have a significant impact on repeat

purchases, i.e., these parts do not influence the consumer's behavior after the purchase. This essay focuses mostly on visual aspects because of their influence on decision-making and emotions.

Research Designs and Methods

In the process of illustration in modern product packaging design, it is difficult to achieve the corporate purpose, because the design process must match and combine factors in product packaging with satisfaction of both entrepreneurs and customers in this stage. This is often very delicate, therefore, the expert system helps to identify system variables and attributes to the experts for the analysis of information supplied by product Packaging about a specific problem consistent with each Factor.

Illustration in Modern Product Design Expert System

Figure 2: Illustration in Modern Product Design Expert System

Based on the Illustration modern product package design expert system graph, there are three primary concerns in this model. Portion (A) represents the entrepreneur's concept, portion (B) represents important key factors analyzed by the Expert, such as the background concept, the identity of the product, the extra value that the expert system can utilize, and the acceptance of the distributor. Finally, portion (C) represents the target of audience of the product. The overall purpose of this paper is to represent the factors in illustration modern packaging decisions.

Concept of Product

The Concept of Product will convey the ideas and concepts (Ideas and Concepts) and to formalize and structure the visual element of style, mood and tone).

Identity Factor

The unique group of companies or brand related to the graphic design and the unique design of the organization today. This is the era of information technology system are bringing modern technology into the graphic design process, equipment and materials to help in the design production to operate efficiently.

Target Group

This is one of the most important activities in marketing management. The entrepreneurs are making is trying to reach everybody and ending up appealing to no one. Therefore in this factor must define the group of the target audience and determine the characteristics of the target audience as well. To define the personality of the illustration of product packaging is suitable for product concept.

Element of Graphic design

To strengthen illustration of product packaging to develop a visually appealing and more attractive by improving and further enhancing your artistic skills and the psychology of perception to help, such as the layout of text, images, colors and size. This is to be proposed as a combination with visual perception.

Aesthetic Factor

Visibility: In the process of visual Communication on illustration of product package. It must have a visual sense of beauty, good impression, good psychological presence, and positive reactions.

Form of packaging: Form of product packaging must be able to match with characteristic of product type before creating a pattern form.

Added Value: Appeal is the way to encourage consumer's desire or need to attract the target consumer demand for the consumption there. Appeal is the main (Theme) of the advertising that will convince with the target audience. What we want to communicate to the target audience in distributor acceptance.

Structure factor

This is a main function of illustration design of product packaging and are concerned about product characteristic and ability of product protection.

Long Term Environmental or Legal Issues

Package development involves considerations for sustainability, environmental responsibility, and applicable environmental and recycling regulations. It may involve a life cycle assessment which considers the material and energy inputs and outputs to the package, the packaged product (contents), the packaging process, the logistics system, waste management, etc. It is necessary to know the relevant regulatory requirements for point of manufacture, sale, and use.

Cost profits

The balance of marketing planning and morphology of budget cost and profits when entrepreneur's launching of the product and distribution is met.

Packaging as a medium of communication information of products

The role of packaging and its functions are dynamic categories; they are shaped in time, mainly influenced by changes in market conditions and needs of consumers, which are closely related to them. The growing requirements of the market, the development of self-service forms of selling, increase in the population wealth as well as increasingly better quality of packaging and possibility of fast modifications caused that packaging has begun to be seen as an important element of any marketing strategy. The role of packaging as a marketing tool largely depends on the nature of a product, for which it is used and the type of the decision, which is taken

by a consumer while the product is bought (Baraniecka, 2002). Until now, packaging has been presented in different contexts in marketing.

- Packaging as an instrument of marketing mix
- Packaging in relation to a product, price, distribution and promotion
- Functions and values of packaging in relation to the needs and requirements of consumers
- Packaging in the strategy of a product
- Packaging in a promotion strategy (advertising, basis for promotion, an element of the brand image)
- Packaging and its design as a source of emotions and experience of consumers
- Packaging as a platform of information and education for consumers.

One of the most important illustration packaging design marketing functions is the communication function, which involves transferring specific information on a given product and its manufacturer to prospective buyers in order to encourage them to buy it. The concept of communication should be understood as both informing, educating as well as promoting a product. It is in this sense that the communication function concerns mainly individual packaging, however it can be noticed that it increasingly expands on collective packaging, which is caused by development of sales networks of the type “Cash and Carry”. The communication function of packaging is usually identified with the aesthetics, visual attractiveness and appropriate information on packaging. This information should primarily shape needs of consumers, attract their attention and arouse their desire to buy a product. The perception of information shown on packaging is a multi-dimensional process, which consists of transmitting information (the cognitive phase), inducing emotions (the affective phase) and action (the behavioral phase). These phases are supposed to result in location of the product in the hierarchy of alternative products taking into account its quality, price as well as brand and arouse the desire of having and buying it.

Product packaging Illustrations

Product packaging makes the application of illustrations more extensive. Product packaging design consists of three elements, symbols, graphics and words. In addition to introducing products, the brand image is also set up at the same time. The most prominent feature, however, is that it is between the plane and the three-dimensional design. The quality of product packaging illustration directly affects the connotation and grade of the product in consumers' impression

This paper proposes the development of a model of illustration of modern packaging design by an expert system. The system will evaluate the successful factors from the entrepreneur's concept, identity, and the mood and tone; this will coincide with the customer's wants and needs. With the use of analysis on multiple forms of design factors, more specifically, identity factors, elements of graphic design, and aesthetic factors, a modified packaging model can be created that will better suit the entrepreneur's concept and the consumer's affinities. When these three main factors are focused on, there will be higher positive result.

Figure 3: Rule-based design system

Using the rule-based design system as shown in *Figure 3*, this can further enhance the illustration of packaging design model. While using a set of rules that the entrepreneur must adhere to, a database of knowledge such as previous data collected about other packaging available in the market, and an algorithm that combines the database and rules, a package design model can be created that successfully shows the entrepreneurs concept, identity, and overall goal of the product. The expert systems enhance the proposed model by analyzing specific information, and analysis of the problem the model could face, and using a specific algorithm that creates a course that can successfully solve the problem.

Conclusion

Illustration in modern Packaging design is traditionally understood as a means of protecting a product in the process of distribution, transport or storage; currently, it is increasingly becoming an effective way to communicate with the environment. On the one hand, it is a consequence of development of various forms of self-service sales and on the other hand, of the growing consumer demand for information as a result of the growing nutritional awareness. Therefore, beside protective or transport functions, illustration in modern packaging must fulfil the information function, particularly in conditions of a limited involvement of sales staff in trade. Packaging is an essential marketing tool, the importance of which is reflected both in the performed functions and the role in the process of making decision on purchase by consumers. It is worth remembering that the first contact of a consumer with a product occurs mostly through packaging. The characteristics of packaging often determine the interest in the product. While the increasing information role of packaging results from many abuses in food production and marketing and common application of additives of unknown effects in future.

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